

Storing Active Research Data

Choosing the right storage for active data depends on your specific needs, budget, and requirements. Effective active data storage ensures fast, reliable, and efficient data access, providing high performance and responsiveness for both applications and users.

Central data storage options:

University of Basel employees can request a group share from [IT-Services \(ITS\)](#) for everyday research documents (e.g. office documents, small to mid-scale research data). For large projects requiring significant storage capacity (tens of TBs or more), [sciCORE](#) offers high-performance storage solutions. Both ITS and sciCORE central storage are regularly backed up.

Advantages of central storage services:

- Professional administration
- Service availability monitored and ensured by the infrastructure provider (ITS or sciCORE)
- Regular and professional maintenance, including infrastructure updates and expansions
- Established and verified disaster recovery concepts
- Comprehensive data backup policy

Check out the website of the Research Data Management Network for more information on [storing research data](#). For specific information and technical support fill out the [contact form](#).

